

EFFECT OF VARIED INTENSITY INTERVAL TRAINING ON SELECTED MOTOR FITNESS COMPONENTS AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL BOYS

Dr. S. Jayasivarajan*, Dr. V. Duraisami & Dr. M. Elayaraja*****

* Associate Professor of Physical Education, Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru College of
Agriculture and Research Institute, Karaikal, Puducherry

** Associate Professor & Head i/c, Department of Yoga, Tamilnadu Physical Education
and Sports University, Chennai, Tamil Nadu

*** Professor, Department of Physical Education, Pondicherry University, Pondicherry

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to compare interval training programmes of different intensity on selected motor fitness components among college boys. For this purpose 45 college boys from karaikal, aged 18 to 21 years took part in the study. Subjects were randomly assigned to three groups of 15 each. Group-I underwent intensive interval training, group-II followed extensive interval training and group-III acted as control subjects. The training regimen lasted for eight weeks. The strength endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and speed were selected as criterion variables, and they were assessed using standard tests and procedures, before and after the training regimen. Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to determine the significant difference existing between pre and post test on selected criterion variables. The analysis of data revealed that both the experimental treatments had significant impact on chosen motor fitness components, however there was significant difference in the level of effectiveness of intensive and extensive interval training on cardio respiratory endurance and speed.

Introduction:

Healthy living and motor fitness are closely connected. Being physically fit not only helps people live healthy lives, it also helps people live longer. People who make physical activity and exercise a part of their daily lives when they are young are more likely to continue the same in their lives as they grow older and benefited throughout their lifespan. Physical activity is defined as any movement that spends energy. Exercise is a subset of physical activity, but it is an activity that is structured and planned. The best way to keep physical activity and exercise a permanent part of one's life is to make it fun and enjoyable. If people are given different options of what they can do and have easy access to those options, they are more likely to participate in physical activity and exercise. This allows people to have a positive attitude toward physical fitness. It's also helpful if people are knowledgeable about the rewards of physical activity and exercise.

The challenges facing the fitness professional is how best they can manipulate training load progressively, and intermix intensity, duration and frequency with a variety of modes of activity, to help the clients reach their goals. Fortunately a number of different training programs are available to the fitness professionals including interval training. Interval training was originated in Europe as a scientific method of developing speed and endurance in athletes. It is a method of overloading the athlete by the use of aerobic and anaerobic exercises, thus developing a high oxygen debt. A quick recovery of cardiovascular and respiratory systems is sought for and expected. In this method, an athlete runs a prescribed course in a specified time for a prescribed number of times. Fast runs are interspersed with short recovery periods of jogging. Besides developing speed and endurance, interval training has the added advantage of allowing large numbers of athletes to train at the same time (Novich & Taylor, 1983). Interval training is a programme of repeated running with a set of interval and restful jogging after each run. The period between runs must be long enough to allow the athlete sometime to recover from previous run, but not long enough to afford him complete recovery (Ecker, 1992).

Doherty (1963) described two types of interval training. The first type is "long interval training" in which one runs half or three quarter of the actual distance at competition speed or even faster, which requires a longer interval of slow jogging. The second type is "short interval training" where, there were two types of workout i.e., pace endurance workout and speed endurance workout. In pace endurance distance pace, intervals are kept constant and the numbers of repetitions are increased as conditions improve. While, the distance interval and the numbers of repetitions are remained fixed and pace varied in speed endurance workout. Intensity, the qualitative component of work an athlete performs in a given time. It is important to establish and use varying degrees of intensity in training. Several methods are available to measure the strength of the stimuli and thus the intensity (Bompa, 1999). The studies of some (Astrand, 1970; Astrand, et al., 1960; Christensen, Hedman & Saltin, 1960) have shown that the alternation of work and rest periods permits more work to be done with less accumulation of lactic acid than work done at the same rate continuously. Furthermore if the duration

of the work period was limited to 10 seconds it was possible to delay fatigue for much longer than when completing 30 or 60 second work bouts under similar 1:2 work/rest ratios (Astrand, et al., 1960). Each method of interval training is designed to achieve specific training goals. The literature on comparative effects and suitability of intensive and extensive interval training on different variables have been insufficiency. Hence, an attempt to compare interval training programmes of different intensity on selected motor fitness components among college boys was made.

Thereby, it was hypothesised that:

- There would be a significant improvement on selected criterion variables due to experimental treatment.
- There would be a significant difference in the level of influence between experimental groups on selected criterion variables.

Methodology:

Subjects:

To achieve the purpose of the study, 45 college boys were selected at random as subjects in the age group of 18 to 21 years. The selected subjects neither have the experience of organised fitness training nor participating in any other special coaching programme. The chosen subjects were randomly segregated into three groups of 15 each. Group-I underwent intensive interval training, group-II followed extensive interval training and group-III acted as control subjects. The duration of the training program as experimental treatment was eight weeks.

Variables:

The independent variables used in the present study were two different intensities of interval training, namely: intensive interval training and extensive interval training. The criterion variables chosen for the present research were strength endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and speed. These criterion variables were assessed using standard tests and procedures, before and after the training regimen. The abdominal strength endurance was tested using bent-knee sit-ups, cardiorespiratory endurance was assessed through Cooper's 12-minute run/walk, and speed was appraised by means of 50 meters dash.

Training Protocol:

The exercise training program of both the experimental groups consisted of sprinting for distance in time and then jogging or walking for a short period that allows incomplete recovery of the heart rate. Fifteen subjects participated in the intensive interval training and fifteen subjects in the extensive interval training program. The subjects confined to both the experimental groups trained one session a day, 3 times a week for 8 weeks in the morning between 6.30 and 8.00 am.

During every session the workout lasted approximately for 90 minutes inclusive of warming up, training and warm down process, while the control group was not exposed to any specific training programme. During every second week of a particular training intensity, one repetition is performed additionally. Further, the prescription of exercise allows two weeks of stabilization to a training intensity, and thereafter the time limit to execute the exercise was reduced so as to increase the intensity of exercise.

Experimental Design:

The experimental design used for the present study was random group design involving 45 volunteers as subjects.

Statistical Techniques:

To examine the efficacy of varied intensity interval training on selected motor fitness components, analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was computed for the data collected from intensive interval training, extensive interval training and control groups during pretest and posttest separately for each variables. Further, since three groups were involved, whenever the F ratio was significant, Scheffé S post hoc test was used to determine which of the paired mean differed significantly. The level of confidence was fixed at 0.05 for significance.

Results and Discussion:

The age, height and weight of the subjects averaged 16.82 ± 0.74 yr, 158.3 ± 3.4 cm, and 56.3 ± 2.52 kg respectively. The data collected on selected motor fitness components before and after eight weeks of intensive and extensive interval training, was analysed by using ANCOVA and it is presented in table 1 & 6 respectively.

Table 1, 3 & 5 shows that the pretest means on abdominal strength endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and speed respectively of intensive interval training, extensive interval training and control groups were found to be insignificantly varied, since the obtained 'F' ratio value was lesser than the required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Further, it demonstrates that the posttest means on abdominal strength endurance, cardiorespiratory endurance and speed respectively of intensive interval training, extensive interval training and control groups were found to be significantly varied, since the obtained 'F' ratio value was greater than the required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Table 1: Analysis of Covariance on Abdominal Strength Endurance of Intensive and Extensive Interval Training and Control Groups

	Intensive Interval Training Group	Extensive Interval Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F Ratio
Pre Test								
Mean	26.20	23.80	23.33	Between	70.978	2	35.489	2.154
S.D	3.028	3.913	4.995	Within	692.133	42	16.479	
Post Test								
Mean	31.33	28.20	23.80	Between	429.644	2	214.822	21.273*
S.D	2.440	3.468	3.509	Within	424.133	42	10.098	
Adjusted Post Test								
Mean	30.289	28.583	24.461	Between	252.468	2	126.234	28.856*
				Within	179.362	41	4.375	

* Significant of 0.05 level of confidence

The required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence with degrees of freedom 2 and 41 is 3.226 and degree of freedom 2 and 42 is 3.222. Table 1 shows that the adjusted posttest means on abdominal strength endurance were found to be significantly varied, since the obtained 'F' ratio value was greater than the required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. Thereby, the analysis of data was further continued and the results of post hoc test on strength endurance are given in table 2.

Table 2: Scheffé' S Test for the Differences between Adjusted Posttest Paired Means on Abdominal Strength Endurance

Adjusted Posttest Mean			Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
Intensive Interval Training Group	Extensive Interval Training Group	Control Group		
30.289	28.583		1.706	1.94
30.289		24.461	5.829*	1.94
	28.583	24.461	4.122*	1.94

*Significant at .05 level.

Table 3: Analysis of Covariance on Cardio Respiratory Endurance of Intensive Interval Training Extensive Interval Training and Control Groups

	Intensive Interval Training Group	Extensive Interval Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F Ratio
Pre Test								
Mean	2049.33	1973.33	2054.7	Between	62098	2	31048.9	2.154
S.D	115.169	64.217	93.417	Within	365600	42	8704.8	
Post Test								
Mean	2247.33	2442.00	2097.33	Between	895951	2	447975.6	56.701*
S.D	84.55	110.66	65.63	Within	331827	42	7900.6	
Adjusted Post Test								
Mean	2237.35	2464.23	2085.09	Between	952299	2	476149.4	73.351*
				Within	266147	41	6491.4	

* Significant of 0.05 level of confidence

The required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence with degrees of freedom 2 and 41 is 3.226 and degree of freedom 2 and 42 is 3.222. Table 3 proves that the adjusted posttest means on cardio respiratory endurance was found to be significantly varied, since the obtained 'F' ratio value was greater than the required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, the analysis of data was further continued and the results of post hoc test on cardio respiratory endurance are given in table 4.

Table 4: Scheffé S Test for the Differences between Adjusted Posttest Paired Means on Cardio Respiratory Endurance

Adjusted Posttest Mean			Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
Intensive Interval Training Group	Extensive Interval Training Group	Control Group		
2237.35	2464.23		-226.879*	74.73
2237.35		2085.09	152.261*	74.73
	2464.23	2085.09	379.140*	74.73

*Significant at .05 level.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance on Speed of Intensive Interval Training Extensive Interval Training and Control Groups

	Intensive Interval Training Group	Extensive Interval Training Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F Ratio
Pre Test								
Mean	7.933	7.867	7.900	Between	0.033	2	0.017	0.531
S.D	0.238	0.150	0.131	Within	1.347	42	0.032	
Post Test								
Mean	7.233	7.467	7.853	Between	895951	2.942	2	25.807*
S.D	0.285	0.184	0.236	Within	331827	2.384	42	
Adjusted Post Test								
Mean	7.193	7.507	7.853	Between	3.252	2	1.626	147.818*
				Within	0.440	41	0.011	

* Significant of 0.05 level of confidence

The required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence with degrees of freedom 2 and 41 is 3.226 and degree of freedom 2 and 42 is 3.222. Table 5 proves that the adjusted posttest means on speed was found to be significantly varied, since the obtained 'F' ratio value was greater than the required table value for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. Thus, the analysis of data was further continued and the results of post hoc test on speed are given in table 6.

Table 6: Scheffé S Test for the Differences between Adjusted Posttest Paired Means on Speed

Adjusted Posttest Mean			Mean Differences	Confidence Interval
Intensive Interval Training Group	Extensive Interval Training Group	Control Group		
7.193	7.507		0.314*	0.097
7.193		7.853	0.660*	0.097
	7.507	7.853	0.346*	0.097

*Significant at .05 level.

The Scheffé S post hoc test reveals that there is a significant influence of both intensive and extensive interval training on abdominal strength endurance, cardio respiratory endurance and speed. Furthermore, it seemed that experimental treatments didn't differ significant among themselves in their level of effectiveness on abdominal strength endurance, while experimental treatments differ significantly at 0.05 level of confidence, in their level of efficiency in upgrading cardio respiratory endurance and speed.

The findings of the present study are in line with the observations of some of the previous empirical researches. Tabata et al., (1996) revealed that steady state group had a higher VO₂max at the end of experimentation, while ultra-intense exercise group had gained anaerobic capacity benefits. A study Little et al., (2009) demonstrated that subjects trained 3 times per week using 60 seconds of intense exercise (at 95% of VO₂max) followed by 75 seconds of rest, repeated for 8-12 cycles, have obtained gains similar to a steady state (50-70% VO₂max) training for five hours per week. A recent study by Driller et al., (2009) showed an improvement that equates to a significant 2% after just 7 interval training sessions.

Conclusion:

It was concluded that both the intensive and extensive interval training regimes are very effective methods of producing a high total work output in a relatively short training session and in improving muscular endurance, cardio respiratory endurance and speed, thereby the ability to tolerate the short duration interval work encountered in many games. Although, these interval training is strenuous and tedious, it can be recommended for individuals who were highly motivated to improve their capacity for performance in competitive sports.

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